

Gender Equality in Institutions of Higher Learning in Zimbabwe: A Case of Midlands State University's Experience with Female Advancement, 2004-2007

Gender equality is rapidly becoming a prerequisite in all spheres of life, both in qualitative and quantitative terms. Institutions of higher learning have not been spared. The consistent lagging behind of women in leadership positions, academic positions and students enrolment in Zimbabwean institutions of higher learning has been the order of the day for quite some time. Recently there have been attempts to address this anomaly. This paper analyses Midlands State University's experience with the quest for gender equality. The paper highlights how the university has sought to bridge gender disparities that have been in existence in institutions of higher learning. It further tries to establish how much ground has been covered in the gender equality crusade vis-à-vis student enrolment and staff recruitment.

Tobias Guzura

Tobias Guzura is a lecturer in Conflict, Peace, Security and Development at the Zimbabwe Open University. He has previously lectured in Gender Studies, Conflict, Peace and Development Studies at the Midlands State University. His research interests are in governance, democracy, human rights, Agrarian issues, gender, Africa's development, security issues and higher education, in which he has substantial publications. Before joining Midlands State University he worked for the Public Service Commission as a high school teacher. He has also held an appointment in a children's welfare organisation. Email: waguzura@gmail.com

Percyslage Chigora

Percyslage Chigora is a lecturer of Political Science at Midlands State University. He serves as the chairperson of the Department of Politics and Public Management. Before joining Midlands State University he worked for an international governmental organisation specialising in project management. He is currently pursuing doctoral studies in the Faculty of Arts, Midlands State University. He is the founding director of a research-oriented non-governmental organisation – the Social Science Research Consultancy Trust. He has researched on Zimbabwe's foreign policy, agrarian issues, Africa's development, security issues, and higher education in which he has published substantially. Email: chigorap2000@yahoo.com

Introduction

Issues of gender in institutions of higher learning, a matter of global importance, have been the subject of debate for some time. One of the major highlights has been the dominance of men in terms of enrolment into programmes as well as the staff, both administrative and academic. For long, old institutions have struggled in theory as well as in practical terms to achieve gender equality. To this end, newly created institutions have faced the same predicament as gender disparities have been in favour of men in all respects. In developing countries the gap has largely remained wide, given the adverse effects of economic and socio-cultural factors. Institutions of higher learning in Zimbabwe have not been spared either, and the sprouting of a number of universities, both state and private, at the turn of the twenty-first century, has met same disparities in terms of gender. Using the case of Midlands State University, which came into being in 2000, the paper seeks to analyse the experiences with issues of gender inequality and the policies that were put in place to address these discrepancies. The overall effects (positive or negative) of the policies will be examined in greater detail with the intention of speculating on the future of female advancement in the institutions of higher learning, not only in Zimbabwe but also in other developing countries and in the world in general.

Conceptual Issues and Historical Background to Gender Equality in Higher Education

Pertinent conceptual issues for the purpose of this research centre around equality, advancement and higher education. In simple terms 'equalism' is a term used to refer to forms of advocacy of equal treatment for those concerned. Thus the equalists believe that society must be perfectly fair to everyone, in this case, irrespective of whether one is male or female. This becomes gender equality, where equalists seek to promote the rights of women and men equally. In practical and specific terms gender equality therefore refers to:

Promoting the equal participation of women and men in making decisions; supporting women and girls so that they can fully exercise their rights; and reducing the gap between women's and men's access to and control of resources and the benefits of development which are still out of reach for most women worldwide.¹

Historically, the struggle for equality has its origins in the writings and practice of John Stuart Mill (1806-1893). Mill during his time as a member of the parliament became the first person to demand voting rights for women.²

Despite the longevity of the struggles for gender equality, realisation of the goal seems to remain far from being achieved. According to the Canadian International Development Agency, women continue to have fewer rights, lower education and health status, less income, and less access to resources and decision-making than men.³

The trends in some sectors, like higher-education, continue to be dominated by lack of gender equality and female advancement, despite calls to address this anomaly. As Mashingaidze rightly observed in relation to Zimbabwe: 'Most people in the Zimbabwean higher education sector seem aware of the need for gender equity and equality but reality on the ground proves otherwise. Women are grossly under-represented as students, lecturers and administrators. Most universities do not have clear-cut gender-mainstreaming policies. Some have affirmative action policies; but these appear to be mere policy frameworks which do not have any significant bearing on reality. There are no gender equity policies with reference to staff recruitment, retention and promotion, as well as staff development policies'.⁴

The historical background of gender disparities and bias in Zimbabwe's education sector has well been articulated by Gudyanga and Chibaya. They have traced this history from the colonial period.⁵ First, 'some education policies served the interests of the white male-dominated colonial socio-economic order. The colonial education system in the then Rhodesia did not have a specific policy for the education of women and girls.'⁶ Secondly, 'the colonial education system had a policy of bottle-necking in the education of African children. Only 12.5% of all African children completing primary education could be

allowed to proceed to secondary education'.⁷ In the end it is the women who were affected most, since socio-culturally, it is perceived as more beneficial to educate a male child than a girl child. In addition to these patriarchal attitudes, religious groups who started schools accessible to all foreign religions also had their negative impacts. For instance, Christianity and Islam introduced 'new patriarchal religious values, women sometimes lost opportunities to occupy important and high positions in society. Christianity is a very male-dominated religion such that women have to fight for leadership roles.'⁸ In addition this comes out of the already-biased traditional society which is male dominated. Hence, the girl suffers from three cultures, i.e. traditional, Christianity and Islamic.

At independence the new government made efforts to restructure the education system. Its policy on education was first enunciated in the ZANU (PF) Party's 1980 Election Manifesto in which the ZANU (PF) government pledged to maintain a uniform educational system, abolish the distinction between African and European education, introduce free and compulsory primary and secondary education for all children regardless of race and above all, to abolish sex discrimination in the education system.⁹

These disparities at lower levels of education adversely affected gender equality at institutions of higher learning. At the time of independence, the number of female students at the University of Zimbabwe, the only university in the country at this time, was very low.¹⁰ The explanation that women were less intelligent to tackle issues of higher learning was in itself a gross misrepresentation of facts, as the real causes stemmed from the education at lower levels which supplied higher education. The reasons for this have been alluded to earlier.

Theory and practice have remained at par for long to the extent that for the first four years into the new millennium the situation had remained grim in terms of achieving gender equality in institutions of higher learning. In fact, Mashingaidze observed that: 'Since the university also served as the training ground for future lecturers, over the years, women have continued to be underrepresented in the Zimbabwean higher education system as students, lecturers and administrators. Men have continued to predominantly occupy most of the executive posts, such as those of deans, librarians, bursars, registrars, pro-vice-chancellors and vice chancellors. Only two universities, namely the Zimbabwe Open University and the Women's University in Africa have female vice chancellors, of the more than a dozen universities in the country. At the Midlands State University, out of the fourteen executive posts, women occupy only three, with one being a librarian and the other two being executive deans. All the Directors are males and even the Deputy Bursar, Deputy Librarian and Deputy Registrar are also males. Resulting from such a scenario at nearly all the universities has been the introduction of a policy of affirmative action by the government'.¹¹

Mashingaidze also captures aptly the policy discrepancies that emerged particularly from what was enunciated in theory and the realities that existed on the ground. According to him: '...in spite of affirmative action policies women still constitute less than a third of the student and teaching staff complements of most Zimbabwean universities. Enrolment figures aside, women are also much marginalised when it comes to leadership positions in student leadership bodies, such as Student Representative Councils, where they constitute less than 20%. The University of Zimbabwe only got its first female in a top post in 1997 with the election of the first female Secretary General Commence Muchena. In May 2004, Gladys Hlatswayo was appointed to the same position, becoming only the second female to occupy one of the top three posts. However, the need for mainstreaming was clearly shown when Muchena resigned from the post in April 1998 due to harassment by male students and lack of support from female students'.¹²

In the 2004/5 academic year, the Midlands State University scored a first when it had the first female SRC president in any of the country's universities.¹³ Such a situation in student politics is representative of the situation at the national level where politics has an androcentric face. National political space is heavily androcentric; with females who dare enter the political fray being viewed as acultural and odd in society. Furthermore, at these institutions, most females fall victim to male instigated harassment especially when they dress in a manner seen as unbecoming by their male counterparts.

Till 2004, the main observations have been ‘women’s increased access to schooling and extended years in education, the knowledge and skills they have acquired in school tend to reproduce rather than alter gender ideologies.’¹⁴ Where strides have been made, though at a slow pace, situation arrived at is that female students are concentrated in the humanities with very few going for the hard/natural sciences. The historical factors of religion that affected lower education in the past have entered into higher education as well, where Christian universities like Solusi, Africa and Catholic universities still emphasise Christian values, which in turn enhance male dominance and female subordination. Thus certain degree programmes become gender discriminatory, while humanities and nursing professions are still dominated by women. Men on the other hand still dominate the sciences, especially the fields of medicine, engineering and architecture. This is perhaps the reason why the National University of Science and Technology, which began operating in 1991, saw an increase in enrolment figures from 1,268 in 1995 to 2,046 in 2000 (an increase of sixty per cent). The proportion of females to total enrolment, however, remained low at nineteen per cent.¹⁵

In essence, therefore, using the total national female population, the general situation was that women (both as students and staff) were clearly under-represented in the institutions of higher learning till 2004 and that included Midlands State University which came into existence in 2000.

The Midlands University’s Experience

Noticing the disparities that have continued in terms of gender equality, the policy makers at Midlands State University formulated policies and took actions to address this perennial problem bedeviling institutions of higher learning. This was done in areas of training, teaching, recruitment of staff and staff development. First, training programmes were designed to sensitise strategic staff in gender issues and mainstreaming as a way of avoiding resistance in policy implementation. Thus strategic staff that included heads of departments, deans and faculty administrators was trained in such areas as basic gender-awareness and sensitisation, gender analysis, gender planning, and the use of gender sensitive indicators in monitoring and evaluation.¹⁶

Secondly, there was a move to introduce modules and programmes to encourage gender awareness particularly to students. This begun with the Midlands State University M.A. degree in Education which has a compulsory gender studies module. This enables all the teachers attending the programme to appreciate the fundamentals of gender issues.¹⁷ The same faculty of education went on to introduce the Department of Gender Studies which offered a compulsory gender module, taught to all students enrolled in the university in level two semester one. The intention here was to sensitise every graduate from the university about gender issues.

In terms of student recruitment there has been an increase in the number of females enrolled in various degree programmes. This was made possible by reducing the number of points for females enrolling into various degree programmes. The diagram below represents the statistics.

Female Student Population Growth Percentages¹⁸

Academic Year	Female Student Population Portion
2000	31.22%
2001	32.22%
2002	37.95%
2003	33.59%
2004	35.67%
2005	38.18%
2006	41.98%
2007	42.36%

It is important to note that despite this phenomenal growth illustrated above, the female student population

has over the years mainly been increasing within the humanities stream. For example, by June 2006, the Faculty of Arts had secured a 56.8 per cent female student population, Education 50.4 per cent, Social Sciences 49.6 per cent and Natural Resources Management and Agriculture 40.7 per cent.¹⁹ The Science and Technology Faculty still show a heavy skew in favour of male students. This gap in policy and action was identified and measures were soon put in place to address the anomaly.

A move was made to introduce a Bridging Programme for females in the natural sciences. Under this programme, females with the bare minimum of advanced level points, enabling them to enter university, underwent a one-semester course meant to bring them at par with their colleagues with higher points. If at the end of the semester they performed well, they were then free to join the programme of their choice in the University Faculty of Science and Technology.

In terms of staff composition the affected sector has been the academic sector and senior management. Out of the total strength of 500 academic staff, the number of females is only 120. The management instituted two main ways of solving this problem. First, recruitment was intentionally made biased towards women. Hereby, in an interview a woman is deemed worthy of selection in preference to a man scoring higher points, and is also offered employment for management and academic posts.

Secondly, for junior academic staff i.e. teaching assistance, bias was shifted towards female candidates and staff development fellowship were awarded to females to encourage them to join academia upon completion of their higher degree programmes.

The results of these policies seemed to be achieving their desired goals, however only in quantitative terms. The unintended policy outcomes are starting to surface in some respects and others are yet to surface. Once they do, the society at large ought to live with these or will have to design ways of circumventing them. The policies and actions have had their negative effects in enabling development of females, not only in these institutions, but the entire society at large. First, resistance came from those who entered the university with high points. These included female and male as well as those males who were left behind by their female counterparts with the same entry qualifications as themselves. These males viewed female students who acquired places at the institution through affirmative action as backdoor intruders. When these females sometimes fail some modules, or get low marks, lecturers also look down on them. The lecturers are not only male but those females who once competed fairly with their male counterparts before the introduction of affirmative action.

Secondly, what seems to have emerged is discrimination against males who come from less-privileged backgrounds. It is assumed that the girl child is worthy of receiving the help. At the same time the truth about affirmative action is that it tends to disregard, and in reality punishes, the disadvantaged boy child. It seems to deny or disregard that there are some males who also have shortcomings that would need to be addressed when they enter the university. For example, there are a number of boys from disadvantaged families or those from Child Headed Household whose performance could also have been affected by their circumstances. But no one seems to take note of these, or care for these students, and they are left to compete on an equal footing with their privileged counterparts. In some instances the females who are beneficiaries of affirmative action are actually better off compared to these disadvantaged males. In this regard, there is an element of marginalisation of the disadvantaged boy, simply because he is a male.

Thirdly, the increase in quantity with regard to female enrolment as well as recruitment has not translated to an increase in quality. Changing ratios towards parity however do not reflect lowering standards or quality either, or that discriminatory factors are embedded in the system. For instance, there is need to move further and examine the promotion of females to males who have been made to retake, repeat, and withdraw modules. There appears to be a disturbing trend that quite a sizable number of the female students admitted under affirmative action either drop out or record below-minimum performance in most of the courses. They cannot cope with the high standards expected of them in comparison to those who fare excellently in their work because they came to the university with good qualifications.

Furthermore, in societies like Zimbabwe, female academics are often torn between opposing career and family responsibilities. This results in added stress for women in workplaces. Family responsibilities

exist for these women as almost a second profession. Here, once the bride price has been paid, expectation of motherhood becomes central for a woman. Any failure in this task often results in societal punishments. In this light, it is hardly surprising why nearly half of the women who stay in academics remain either single, childless or divorced, raising the question of how work/family conflicts influence the choices women make.²⁰ This in turn raises an important issue because the university, more than any other place of employment, is highly influenced by the life outside of work, and are training grounds for future leaders. Universities therefore need to offer an effective model on how to balance family and career towards the betterment of the individual in particular and the entire society in general.

In addition, societal attitudes towards pregnancy and marriage continue to mean that some girls do not complete school because they get embroiled in family care at an early point in their lives, making academic careers practically impossible to pursue. The overlapping of their peak childbearing years and period of pursuing tenure make academic jobs increasingly difficult for them.²¹

Lastly, when policies are instituted there is often a tendency to discriminate in a much more subtle and systemic way. According to Hensel Nancy this is because, 'Academia has long been dominated by men, and the male perspective in policy development, performance evaluation, and interpersonal interactions generally prevails. Student evaluations indicate that women's classroom performance is often evaluated more critically than men's. Research by women or about women is frequently undervalued by male colleagues. Initial salary differentials between men and women increase in favor of men as faculty progress through the ranks. Women take two to ten years longer than men to achieve promotion and tenure; women's greater child care responsibilities may account for some of this differential. Each of these issues leads to a cumulative disadvantage for the female professor. Women who earn doctorates are more likely than men to desire an academic career but are not being hired at equal rates; the cumulative disadvantage also results in women leaving the profession in greater numbers than men'.²²

As institutions of higher learning continue their attempt to achieve gender equality, there is need to move further and address some pertinent issues to enable the success of the policies. First, considerable efforts have been made to improve access to schooling and, in particular, to target female enrolment. On a more radical stance, abolition of fees for the girl child appears to be the most drastic step, as poverty affects the schooling opportunities of girls. On a more practical note, having a girl child at an institution of higher learning on government sponsorship will motivate the females and do away with segregation that comes with poverty.

Secondly, instead of continuing to admit female students with lower points, the disparities that cause performance gaps should be addressed. This should only be done at lower levels of education where incentives and policy measures are put in place to give support for the attainment of higher grades, rather than waiting to solve the problem using affirmative action later. Here political will plays a much more important role. At times the institution might also consider introducing catch-up programmes for a year, before the students are admitted into their main degree programmes.

Lastly, formal and informal policies which consider the needs of diverse individuals must be broadly adopted and enforced.²³ Putting all females in the same category seems to be the major cause of the negative after-effects of the policies. For instance, if one were to take two cases, one of a girl who grew up in a low density suburb and had no domestic chores to perform, and another girl from a rural background who had to walk long distances to and from her school and also had to take care of some household work, their experiences will be entirely different. In case they both secure low points in the same subject, questions like who should get affirmative action benefit, and with what effect, will definitely arise. Therefore in designing, implementing and evaluating these policies, closer and more careful analysis should be done.

Conclusion

In conclusion it is important to highlight that gender equality and other efforts to enhance female advancement in institutions of higher learning have remained a challenge despite certain quantitative improvements. In essence, obstacles to women's participation in higher education still very much exist.

As the present paper has argued, though there is a call for gender mainstreaming the recruitment, enrolments, promotions and organisational structures, there are still underlying structural and societal impediments towards a full realisation of female advancement. Achieving gender equality hinges on collective and social responsibility for the consequences that come alongside the need to promote gender equality, not only for the concerned institutions but also for the government and the society at large.

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